

Applicability of Glassy Carbon Electrode in Combination with Platinum for Biamperometric Indication : Determination of 2-Mercaptoethanol using Potassium Iodate in Aqueous Medium

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Glassy carbon has recently been applied as a successful electrode for several electrometric estimations with definite advantages¹. Its combination with platinum to provide a suitable electrode system has now been investigated for use in biamperometry. We report here the suitability of this glassy carbon-Pt system for the estimation of 2-mercaptoethanol using potassium iodate as an oxidant exploiting iodine-iodide as the current-indicating reversible couple. Mercaptans constitute an important class of sulphur compounds. Numerous methods have been employed depending on the specific requirement, amongst which the one involving redox process (producing a disulphide) appears to be very common,

In addition to the oxidimetric method, others which have been useful in aqueous medium are based on exploitation of its reaction with metal ions like lead², silver³ and mercury⁴, wherein the end-point has been detected mostly electrometrically^{4,5}. A survey of literature reveals studies on the oxidation of water soluble potassium iodate⁶, 2-mercaptobenzothiazole coulometrically⁷ and 2-mercaptoethanol on a graphite electrode modified with metal phthalocyanines⁸. The oxidation of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole and 2-mercaptobenzimidazole in aqueous solution was also studied by d.c. voltammetry on a rotating Pt and a rotating glassy carbon disk electrode⁹. Later on Murthy and co-workers¹⁰ established the optimum conditions required for studying the oxidation of thiols by sodium *N*-haloaryl sulphonamides. In a mixed solvent of acetonitrile and methanol, Verma and coworkers¹¹ utilised both the visual and potentiometric methods for its determination with ICl, ICl₃, iodobenzene dichloride and *n*-bromosuccinimide. Some of the aliphatic and aromatic mercaptans have been estimated by Ghosh and Prasad¹² using copper(II) perchlorate and also iodine in non-aqueous media employing platinum-graphite biamperometric indication. Verma and Sood¹³ reported that the direct titration of mercaptans using copper(II) perchlorate in acetonitrile being slow (particularly at later stage) an indirect method is better suited.

The present work is an attempt for testing the applica-

bility of the glassy carbon-platinum electrode combination of aqueous estimation of mercaptan involving iodine-iodide couple. Instead of direct iodine solution, the use of potassium iodate was preferred to provide iodine at the moment needed, as direct titration with iodine have been observed to be slow. The mercaptan selected as a test case was a water-soluble one. An exhaustive study was made in light of the reproducibility and the precision of results with varied small amounts and various applied e.m.f. values.

Results and Discussion

The present estimations being based primarily on the oxidimetric process. The general reaction forming the basis of the present estimation may be represented¹⁴ as

Under the described conditions of titration, mercaptans are oxidised to disulphides. The end-point is indicated although visually by the appearance of the iodine colour formed by first drop in excess but in the present biamperometric method sudden increase in current values has been taken to mark the completion of the process. It is thus evident from the above reaction that any extra titrant added generates iodine causing the inception of the iodine-iodide couple. As such therefore, the current-volume plots are of the same nature (Fig. 1) as in the direct use of iodine. A sudden onset of the cell current showing increase thereafter on further addition is anticipated to yield a titration curve of reversed L-shaped as actually observed, and at the same time, seems to be independent of the magnitude of the polarising e.m.f. The breaks (indicative of the equivalence points) are found to be invariably unambiguous. It simply enhances the current value. It is to be noted that the technique is essentially similar to that of conventional biamperometry with identical platinum electrodes¹⁵. The dissimilarity of the present electrode system helps to produce well-defined breaks. The percentage error is restricted within a narrow range of $\pm 1\%$.

It is thus evident that present technique is simple, avoids much of instrumentation and is precise. The combination of glassy carbon electrode with platinum is well-suited with

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iodine-iodide couple in aqueous medium, indicating that the technique is reliable for such estimations involving low concentrations.

Fig. 1. Volume of KI solution against current plots: (A) 15.45 mg, 50 mV, (B) 16.03 mg, 100 mV and (C) 13.99 mg, 150 mV.

Experimental

The experimental technique was essentially the same as applied for wax impregnated graphite-platinum electrode system¹⁶. A glassy carbon and a micro-platinum electrode fitted tightly in a rubber disc with fixed interspace of ~3 cm (having necessary holes for burette tip and for the passage of nitrogen gas) constituted the electrode assembly between which a constant e.m.f. was applied from a battery operated potentiometer.

Chemicals used were of analytical grade except stated otherwise. The test solution of 2-mercaptoethanol (Fluka) was prepared in double-distilled water and standardised using iodine in aqueous medium. Potassium iodate solution was prepared¹⁷ in double-distilled water.

Procedure: A known amount of the test solution taken in the titration vessel was diluted to 30 ml with water. The electrode assembly was then inserted and a requisite e.m.f. impressed between the electrode with glassy carbon as the positive. The solution was kept agitated using a magnetic stirrer and a slow stream of nitrogen gas was bubbled into the cell prior to and also throughout the titration. The titrant was administered from semi-microburette and the test solution was titrated with KIO_3 in presence of H_2SO_4 and KI. The cell current was measured after 2 min following each addition of the titrant with a sensitive galvanometer.

TABLE I—ESTIMATION OF 2-MERCAPTOETHANOL USING GLASSY CARBON AND PLATINUM COMBINATION FOR BIAMPEROMETRIC INDICATION IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM USING POTASSIUM IODATE

Applied e.m.f. (mV)	Approx. molarity $\times 10^{-3} M$	Amount of substances (mg)		Error %
		Taken	Found	
50	2.3	5.45	5.45	0.00
	4.6	10.91	10.89	-0.18
	7.0	16.36	16.34	-0.12
	9.1	21.82	21.79	-0.14
	1.2	27.27	27.24	-0.11
100	1.7	4.01	4.01	0.00
	3.4	8.01	8.01	0.00
	6.8	16.03	16.02	-0.06
	8.5	20.03	20.17	+0.70
150	1.5	3.48	3.49	+0.28
	3.0	6.95	6.97	-0.29
	4.4	10.44	10.46	+0.19
	5.9	13.91	13.99	+0.57
	7.4	17.38	17.48	-0.57

The equivalence point was obtained from the corresponding plots of current versus volume of the titrant added. The results obtained with the amounts (3.49–27.24 mg) are summarised in Table 1.

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